

Deletion of lymphatic PD-L1 protects mice from severe autoimmune encephalitis

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Abstract

Lymph node-resident lymphatic endothelial cells (LECs) present self-antigens and constitutively express the checkpoint molecule PD-L1. Furthermore, PD-L1 is induced in peripheral LECs in inflammatory conditions, including in brain-associated LECs at the cribriform plate during autoimmune encephalitis (EAE). Consequently, it has been suggested that lymphatic PD-L1 might be important for self-tolerance and the prevention of autoimmune diseases, including in the brain.

Surprisingly, we observed that mice lacking lymphatic PD-L1 expression were partially protected from EAE and developed less severe symptoms than controls in a classic EAE model induced by myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein (MOG) immunization. This protection was associated with increased expression of CTLA4 in brain-infiltrating, regulatory CD8⁺ T cells expressing the transcription factors Foxp3 and Helios. In contrast, lymphatic PD-L1 deletion had no impact on T cells in brain-draining cervical lymph nodes at the peak of the disease nor in peripheral, skin-draining LNs in response to MOG vaccination.

Thus, our findings suggest that inhibition of PD-L1 in specific cell types like LECs could be beneficial in the context of autoimmune neuroinflammation.

Introduction

The lymphatic vascular system plays a pivotal role in the regulation of adaptive immune responses, not only through transport of antigen and immune cells to and from lymph nodes (LNs) but also through direct immune-regulatory functions of lymphatic endothelial cells (LECs) (1). Remarkably, LN-resident LECs constitutively express PD-L1 (2, 3), particularly in LEC subsets lining the floor of the subcapsular sinus and medullary sinuses (4). In addition, peripheral LECs that typically do not express PD-L1 may upregulate its expression in the context of inflammation and cancer (5, 6). At the same time, LECs act as “sessile” antigen-presenting cells that can scavenge and present endogenous as well as exogenous antigen in the context of MHC-I and -II to both CD8⁺ and CD4⁺ T cells (7, 8). Consequently, it has been proposed that LECs may impair T cell-mediated immune responses, potentially contributing to peripheral self-tolerance in steady state and moderating T cell responses in pathological, inflammatory conditions (3, 9, 10). In line with this, we previously found that transgenic mice that lack PD-L1 expression in LECs (PD-L1^{LECKO}) show elevated CD8⁺ T cell responses against tumor antigens (11). However, there is currently no direct, experimental evidence that lymphatic PD-L1 is required to control autoimmunity against self-antigens *in vivo*. Previously considered an immune-privileged site, work over the past decade has demonstrated that the central nervous system (CNS) is drained by lymphatic vessels (12). Meningeal and perinervous lymphatic vessels at the base of the skull have all been implicated in the drainage of brain-derived antigens to cervical LNs for the regulation of adaptive immune responses within the CNS. At least in mice, lymphatic vessels associated with the cribriform plate (CP) and connected to the dense lymphatic network in the nasal mucosa appear to account for a major fraction of the CNS drainage

(13). Interestingly, a recent study by Hsu and colleagues found that CP-associated lymphatic vessels strongly upregulate PD-L1 expression in the context of experimental autoimmune encephalitis (EAE), a mouse model of multiple sclerosis (MS) driven by CD4⁺ T cells specific for a peptide derived from myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein (MOG) (14). Furthermore, the authors found that CP-associated LECs were presenting brain-derived antigens, and that PD-L1 blockade on cultured CP LECs could enhance the activation of MOG-specific, CD4⁺ 2D2 T cells *ex vivo* (14). However, it is currently unclear whether lymphatic PD-L1 expression is relevant for EAE severity *in vivo*. Here, we challenged PD-L1^{LECKO} mice with a classic EAE model elicited by MOG peptide vaccination. Surprisingly, we found that lymphatic PD-L1 deletion did not exacerbate neuroinflammation. In contrast, we observed a significant protective effect of lymphatic PD-L1 deletion, which was associated with an inhibitory phenotype of CNS-infiltrating CD8⁺ T cells, particularly in a subset expressing the transcription factor Helios, warranting further studies of the underlying mechanisms with potential implications for the clinical management of MS.

Material and Methods

Mice: PD-L1^{LECKO} mice (Prox1-Cre-ER^{T2} x Cd274^{fl/fl}) on a C57Bl/6 background have been described previously (11) and were bred under SOPF conditions. To induce Cre-mediated recombination, 50 mg/kg tamoxifen (Sigma) in sunflower oil (Sigma) were administered by i.p. injection for 5 days. Cre-negative Cd274^{fl/fl} littermates served as controls and were equally treated with tamoxifen. All animal procedures were reviewed and approved by the Swiss Veterinary Office and performed according to institutional and federal guidelines.

Experimental autoimmune encephalitis (EAE) model: To elicit neuroinflammation, sex matched, adult male and female mice between 8-12 weeks of age, were immunized with MOG peptide as described previously (15). In brief, 200 µg of MOG₃₅₋₅₅ peptide (Genscript) emulsified in complete Freund's adjuvant (BD) were injected s.c. and 100 ng pertussis toxin (List Biological Laboratories, 179A) was injected i.p. on the day of immunization and again 2 days after. Scoring of EAE symptoms was done as follows: 0: no signs of EAE; 0.5: tail limp at distal end; 1: entire limp tail; 1.5: limp tail and hind limb weakness; 2: unilateral partial hind limb paralysis; 2.5: bilateral partial hind limb paralysis; 3: complete bilateral hind limb paralysis; 3.5: complete bilateral hind limb and partial forelimb paralysis; 4: complete hind and forelimb paralysis (moribund). 0.5 scoring intervals were used to allow a more accurate description of the clinical symptoms.

Tissue processing and flow cytometry: Peripheral axillary and inguinal LNs, CNS-draining superficial cervical LNs and brain were collected at the indicated timepoints and processed for flow cytometry. For leukocyte analysis, LNs and brain were digested using 0.4 mg/ml Collagenase IV (Sigma) and 0.2 mg/ml DNase 1 (Luzerna) in HBSS for 40 min at 37°C. Subsequently, the material was mechanically dissociated using a 19-gauge needle and filtered through a 100 µm cell strainer to obtain a single cell suspension. In the case of brain samples, leukocytes were further enriched by 30% Percoll gradient centrifugation. For analysis of LN stromal cells, LN samples were digested as described previously (16). In brief, LN capsules were broken using needles, followed by sequential digestion with 1 mg/ml and then 3.5 mg/ml Collagenase IV

(Gibco) in DMEM supplemented with 2% FBS (Gibco) and 1.2 mM CaCl₂. Finally, the material was passed through a 40 µm cell strainer to obtain a single cell suspension. FACS staining was done on ice using fluorescently conjugated primary antibodies (Supplementary Table 1) in combination with an Fc-blocker (rat anti-mouse CD16/32, clone 93, Biolegend). Intracellular staining was achieved using the Foxp3 staining buffer kit (eBioscience) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Data were acquired on a 5-laser Aurora spectral analyzer (Cytex Biosciences) or a FACS Aria II (BD) and analyzed using FlowJo (BD) and / or unbiased high-parametric data projection and clustering (17). To this end, unmixed flow cytometry data were compensated using FlowJo v10.10.0, and populations of interest were exported. Equal numbers of cells were exported from each sample and then imported into R (v4.4.2). The CyCombine package was utilized to combine the population of interest. After an arcsinh transformation and a percentile normalization of the values between 0 and 1, the transformed and normalized data were projected using the Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) algorithm. Unsupervised clustering was conducted using the FlowSOM algorithm, with the number of clusters selected based on the marker projection within the UMAP to ensure meaningful clustering. Plots were created using the ggplot2 package and statistical tests using Student's t-test analysis.

Results

Lymphatic PD-L1 deletion is protective in autoimmune neuroinflammation

To investigate the function of lymphatic PD-L1 in the context of autoimmune neuroinflammation, we used conditional PD-L1^{LECKO} mice in which PD-L1 is deleted upon Tamoxifen application in Prox1+ LECs (11). Flow cytometry analysis of peripheral LN stromal cells confirmed efficient PD-L1 deletion in Prox1⁺ LECs, whereas PD-L1

expression in Prox1⁻ blood endothelial cells and fibroblastic reticular cells was not affected (Supplementary Fig. 1). After immunization with an MHC-II-restricted peptide derived from the self-antigen MOG, both PD-L1^{LECKO} (Cre+) and littermate controls (Cre-) developed typical symptoms of EAE, with a similar lag time until disease onset (Fig. 1A). Surprisingly however, two-way ANOVA analysis of the EAE scores indicated a small but significantly improved outcome for Cre+ mice (Fig. 1A). This resulted in a trend towards longer survival (Fig. 1B) and a significantly reduced rate of mice developing severe symptoms (clinical score ≥ 3) of Cre+ compared to Cre- mice (Fig. 1C). Taken together, these data show that deletion of lymphatic endothelial PD-L1 expression unexpectedly protects mice from severe EAE.

Lymphatic PD-L1 deletion minimally affects T cell priming after immunization

LN-resident LECs constitutively express PD-L1 (3). Therefore, deletion of lymphatic PD-L1 expression before MOG immunization could have an impact on the initial T cell priming, even before manifestation of the disease. To test this hypothesis, we collected peripheral LNs (inguinal, axillary, brachial) draining the site of immunization and assessed their immune cell composition by multiparameter flow cytometry on day 6 after immunization (Fig. 2A). First, we quantified the frequencies of all TCRb⁺ CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells, but found no difference between the groups (Fig. 2B). Subsequently, we distinguished major effector / memory and regulatory CD4⁺ T cell subsets based on expression of Foxp3 (Fig. 2C), CD44 and CD62L. As expected after MOG immunization, we noticed a robust CD4⁺ T cell response, evidenced by a large proportion of cells with an activated, CD44⁺ CD62L⁻ phenotype. However, the frequency of this and other CD4⁺ T cell subsets was equal in Cre+ and Cre- mice (Fig. 2D), and the expression levels of

activation-regulated markers and effector molecules were not affected (Fig. S2A-D). Similarly, CD8⁺ T cells showed very similar frequencies and phenotypes in Cre⁺ and Cre⁻ mice, with only minor changes in expression of GITR and Ly6C (Fig. 2E, 2F, S2E-H). Finally, we also analyzed TCRβ⁻ immune cells in the LN microenvironment. Using unsupervised clustering of FACS data we identified several subsets including B cells, dendritic cells and monocytes (Fig. S2I, S2J), but could not detect any significant differences between Cre⁺ and Cre⁻ mice either (Fig. S2K). Thus, deletion of lymphatic PD-L1 expression has no major impact on the immune response towards the initial MOG immunization.

CNS infiltration by regulatory CD8⁺ T cells increases when lymphatic PD-L1 is deleted

As the rate to develop severe EAE appeared attenuated in Cre⁺ mice especially from day 10 after immunization and onwards (Fig. 1C), we next decided to analyze immune landscapes in both the inflamed CNS and CNS-draining cervical LNs in Cre⁺ and Cre⁻ mice on day 13 after immunization (Fig. 3A), using a similar flow cytometry gating approach as before. The frequency of CNS-infiltrating CD45⁺ leukocytes as well as TCRβ⁺ CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells was unaffected by lymphatic PD-L1 knockout (Fig. 3B, 3C). To define T cell subsets, we included staining for the transcription factor Helios as marker of Treg stability (18). As expected, most CNS-infiltrating Tregs were Helios⁺, indicating a stable Treg phenotype, whereas CD4⁺ non-Tregs were prominently CD44⁺ and CD62L⁻ (Fig. 3D). The frequencies of the individual CD4⁺ T cell subsets were equal in Cre⁺ and Cre⁻ mice (Fig. 3E). Similarly, there was no apparent difference in the phenotype of CNS-infiltrating CD4⁺ cells, with the exception of slightly reduced CD38

expression by Helios⁺ cells in Cre⁺ mice, perhaps indicating reduced activation (Fig. 3F, S3A-F).

CD4⁺ effector T cells are considered to be the main drivers behind CNS pathology in the EAE model. In contrast, the role of CD8⁺ T cells in this disease is much less well understood. While CD8⁺ T cells expand and infiltrate inflamed brains, several reports suggest that these cells rather have a regulatory than a pathological function during the disease (19, 20). Curiously, we noted a clear population of Foxp3⁺ regulatory T cells among the CD8⁺ CNS infiltrate, most of which were Helios⁺ (Fig. 3G). A sizeable fraction of CD8⁺ T cells in inflamed brains were Helios⁺ and Foxp3⁻, whereas very few cells were Foxp3⁺ Helios⁻ (Fig. 3G). A closer inspection of the frequencies and phenotype of CD8⁺ T cell subsets revealed that Foxp3⁺ Helios⁺ regulatory CD8⁺ T cells were increased in the CNS of mice lacking lymphatic PD-L1 ($p = 0.055$, Fig. 3H). Additionally, these cells showed significantly increased expression of CTLA4, suggesting a more inhibitory phenotype (Fig. 3I, S3G-3L). Thus, reduced disease severity in mice lacking lymphatic PD-L1 was accompanied by increased CNS infiltration of a regulatory CD8⁺ T cell subset expressing high levels of Foxp3, Helios, and CTLA4.

Finally, we also charted the non-T immune landscape in the CNS of mice on day 13 after MOG immunization, using markers for B cells and innate immune cells, using unsupervised clustering to identify relevant cellular subsets. However, no difference in any of the cell clusters between Cre⁻ and Cre⁺ mice could be observed (Fig. S3M-O).

T cells in brain-draining LNs are not affected by lymphatic PD-L1 deletion

As PD-L1 expression was found to be upregulated in LECs at the cribriform plate of mice subjected to EAE (14), we reasoned that it might impair particularly those T cells exiting

the brain via the lymphatic system en route to draining cervical LNs. However, flow cytometry-based quantification and immunophenotyping of cervical LNs did not result in any major differences between the groups, neither with regards to CD4⁺ T cells, CD8⁺ T cells, nor non-T immune cells (Fig. 4, Fig. S4).

Taken together, these data show that lymphatic PD-L1 deletion polarizes brain-infiltrating CD8⁺ T cells towards an immune-inhibitory phenotype during EAE, particularly those expressing Helios. Potentially, this immune-inhibitory T cell profile is responsible for the alleviation of EAE symptoms we observed in PD-L1^{LECKO} mice.

Discussion

LN-resident LECs have been implicated in the maintenance of peripheral self-tolerance, due to their promiscuous expression and presentation of a range of peripheral tissue self-antigens and concomitant expression of PD-L1, resulting in the elimination of autoreactive CD8⁺ T cells (2, 3, 7, 21). Furthermore, LN LECs express MHC-II and have been reported to promote the conversion of CD4⁺ T cells into Tregs (10). Recently, Hsu et al found that cribriform plate-associated LECs upregulate PD-L1 expression during EAE (14). Furthermore, blockade of PD-L1 could enhance LEC-mediated activation of MOG-specific CD4⁺ T cells *ex vivo* (14), a finding that is in line with our own previous work in which PD-L1 blockade or deletion enhanced priming of T cells specific for a model antigen *in vitro* (5, 11). Based on those observations, PD-L1 expressing LECs were suggested to control EAE severity (14). However, there is no direct evidence yet that LEC-expressed PD-L1 is required for self-tolerance or that it could limit autoimmunity *in vivo*.

Here, we surprisingly found that deletion of PD-L1 from both the peripheral and LN lymphatic endothelium did not aggravate clinical symptoms of EAE. In contrast, lack of PD-L1 on LECs partially protected mice from developing severe EAE. This was associated with an immune-inhibitory phenotype of brain-infiltrating CD8⁺ T cells in mice lacking lymphatic PD-L1 expression, characterized by an expansion of Foxp3⁺ Helios⁺ cells expressing elevated CTLA4 levels.

At first glance, our findings appear at odds with the well-known function of PD-L1, inhibiting PD-1⁺ effector T cells. However, the disease context and contribution of distinct T cell subsets to disease pathology deserve consideration. For example, PD-1 is not only expressed by activated effector T cells but is also expressed by Tregs. In fact, a previous study found that deletion of PD-1 from Foxp3⁺ Tregs ameliorated the disease course in the EAE model, suggesting that PD-L1 / PD-1 signaling controls Treg activity (22). In line with this, deletion of lymphatic PD-L1 might unleash Tregs, increasing their immune-inhibitory activity and thereby controlling EAE progression. Of note, some reports have already pointed to an immune-inhibitory, disease controlling function of CD8⁺ T cells in this context (19, 20), reconciling our observations with the well-established functions of PD-L1 as an immune checkpoint.

It is curious that lymphatic PD-L1 predominantly affected regulatory CD8⁺ T cells expressing the transcription factor Helios. Among CD4⁺ T cells, Helios has been used as marker for thymus-derived and phenotypically stable Tregs (18, 23). In contrast, the origin and function of Helios⁺ CD8⁺ T cells is not well understood. It has been suggested that Helios is upregulated in senescent CD8⁺ T cells with limited effector functions and is required for CD8⁺ Tregs (24-26). Yet, brain-infiltrating Helios⁺ CD8⁺ T cells in EAE showed only intermediate PD-1 expression, suggesting that they were not exhausted.

Instead, enhanced CTLA4 expression in this subset upon lymphatic PD-L1 deletion suggests an active, immune-inhibitory function in the brain.

Based on our data, it is not possible to conclude whether CTLA4 upregulation in brain-infiltrating T cells is responsible for the improved disease outcome in mice lacking lymphatic PD-L1, or if this phenotype is rather a consequence of reduced brain inflammation. Clearly, further studies perturbing regulatory CD8⁺ T cells or their CTLA4 expression in CD8⁺ T cells *in vivo* would be required to dissect the underlying mechanisms. Nonetheless, our data support the notion that PD-L1-expressing LECs provide highly context-dependent input to CD8⁺ T cell immunity and disease outcomes, not only restraining effector T cells in the context of e.g. tumor immunity (11) but potentially also inhibiting Tregs.

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Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Figures

Fig.1

Figure 1: Lymphatic PD-L1 deletion protects from severe EAE. (A) Cre- (N = 15) and Cre+ mice (N = 14) were treated with tamoxifen and subsequently immunized with MOG₃₅₋₅₅. Clinical symptoms were scored over time and mice were euthanized when a score of 4 was reached. * p < 0.05 (two-way ANOVA test). (B) Kaplan-Meier survival curve of the same mice as in (A). (C) Proportion of mice from (A) developing severe EAE (score 3 or higher). * p < 0.05 (Log-rank test).

Fig.2

Figure 2: Lymphatic PD-L1 deletion does not affect the initial T cell response to MOG immunization.

(A) Schematic of the experimental approach. (B) Frequency of TCRb⁺ CD4⁺ and TCRb⁺ CD8⁺ T cells among all living singlet CD45⁺ cells. (C) Total LN cells pregated for living singlet TCRb⁺ CD4⁺ were gated into Foxp3⁺ Treg and Foxp3⁻ non-Treg. (D) Frequency of major CD4⁺ T cell subsets (Foxp3⁺ Treg, Foxp3⁻ CD44⁺ CD62L⁻, Foxp3⁻ CD44⁺ CD62L⁺, Foxp3⁻ CD44⁻ CD62L⁺) in peripheral LNs. (E) Total LN cells pregated for living singlets TCRb⁺ CD8⁺ were gated into Foxp3⁺ Treg and Foxp3⁻ non-Treg. (F) Frequency of major CD8⁺ T cell subsets (Foxp3⁺ Treg, Foxp3⁻ CD44⁺ CD62L⁻, Foxp3⁻ CD44⁺ CD62L⁺, Foxp3⁻ CD44⁻ CD62L⁺) in peripheral LNs. N = 6 mice / group.

Fig.3

Figure 3: Lymphatic PD-L1 depletion amplifies regulatory CD8+ T cells in the inflamed CNS. (A) Schematic of the experimental approach. (B) Frequency of CD45+ cells infiltrating the CNS. (C) Frequency of TCRb+ CD4+ and TCRb+ CD8+ T cells in the

CNS. (D) Pregated living singlet TCRb+ CD4+ cells were divided into 6 subsets depending on the expression of HELIOS, Foxp3, CD44 and CD62L. (E) Frequency of these CD4+ subsets in the CNS on day 13 after immunization. (F) Expression (mean intensity) of CTLA4 and CD38 among these CD4+ subsets. (G) Pregated living singlet TCRb+ CD8+ cells were divided into 6 subsets depending on the expression of HELIOS, Foxp3, CD44 and CD62L. (H) Frequency of these CD8+ subsets in the CNS on day 13 after immunization. (I) Expression (mean intensity) of CTLA4 and CD38 among these CD8+ subsets. N = 6 mice / group. Student's t-test was used to test for significant differences.

Fig.4

Figure 4: The T cell composition of cervical LNs is not affected by lymphatic PD-L1 deletion during autoimmune neuroinflammation. (A) Schematic of the experimental

approach. (B) Frequency of TCRb⁺ CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells in cervical LNs. (C) Pregelated living singlet TCRb⁺ CD4⁺ cells were divided into 6 subsets depending on the expression of HELIOS, Foxp3, CD44 and CD62L. (D) Frequency of these CD4⁺ subsets in cervical LNs on day 13 after immunization. (E) Expression (mean intensity) of CTLA4 and CD38 among these CD4⁺ subsets. (F) Pregelated living singlet TCRb⁺ CD8⁺ cells were divided into 6 subsets depending on the expression of HELIOS, Foxp3, CD44 and CD62L. (G) Frequency of these CD8⁺ subsets in the CNS on day 13 after immunization. (H) Expression (mean intensity) of CTLA4 and CD38 among these CD8⁺ subsets. N = 6 mice / group.

Supplementary Figures

Fig. S1

Figure S1: Flow cytometry quantification of PD-L1 expression in peripheral LN stromal cells of PD-L1^{LECKO} mice. (A) Gating strategy to analyze LN stromal cell subsets blood endothelial cells (BEC, CD45⁻ CD31⁺ Podoplanin⁻), fibroblastic reticular cells (FRC, CD45⁻ CD31⁻ Podoplanin⁺) and lymphatic endothelial cells (LEC, CD45⁻ CD31⁺ Podoplanin⁺). (B-D) Representative histograms of PD-L1 expression in BECs, FRCs and LECs after tamoxifen application and MOG vaccination. Red curve: Cre-negative; blue

curve: Cre-positive; grey curve: isotype control staining. (E-G) Quantification of PD-L1 expression in peripheral LN BECs, FRCs, and LECs. N = 6 mice / group, **** p < 0.0001

Fig. S2

A) CD4+ Foxp3+ Treg

B) CD4+ CD44+ CD62L-

C) CD4+ CD44+ CD62L+

D) CD4+ CD44- CD62L+

E) CD8+ Foxp3+ Treg

F) CD8+ CD44+ CD62L-

G) CD8+ CD44+ CD62L+

H) CD8+ CD44- CD62L+

I) TCRb- UMAP

J) TCRb- Heat Map of Cluster Markers

K) TCRb- Frequency of Cells / cluster

Figure S2: Analysis of immune landscape in peripheral LNs on day 6 after MOG

immunization. (A-D) Phenotypic characterization of CD4+ T cell subsets Treg (A),

CD44+CD62L- effector / memory (B), CD44+CD62L+ central memory (C) and CD44-CD62L+ naïve cells (D) by flow cytometry. (E-H) Phenotypic characterization of CD8+ T cell subsets Treg (E), CD44+CD62L- effector / memory (F), CD44+CD62L+ central memory (G) and CD44-CD62L+ naïve cells (H) by flow cytometry. (I-K) Multidimensional flow cytometry analysis of TCR- immune cells in peripheral LNs draining the site of immunization on day 6. (I) Unsupervised clustering and (J) heat map with marker expression in the individual immune cell clusters. (K) Proportion of each of the clusters in Cre- compared to Cre+ mice (N = 6 mice / group). Grzmb: Granzyme B.

Fig. S3

Figure S3: Analysis of immune landscape in the inflamed CNS on day 13 after immunization. (A-F) Phenotypic characterization of CD4+ T cell subsets distinguished by HELIOS, Foxp3, CD44 and CD62L by flow cytometry. (G-L) Phenotypic characterization of CD8+ T cell subsets distinguished by HELIOS, Foxp3, CD44 and

CD62L by flow cytometry. (M-O) Multidimensional flow cytometry analysis of TCR-immune cells in CNS on day 13 after immunization. (M) Unsupervised clustering and (N) heat map with marker expression in the individual immune cell clusters. (O) Proportion of each of the clusters in Cre- compared to Cre+ mice (N = 6 mice / group).

Fig. S4

Figure S4: Analysis of immune landscape in cervical LNs on day 13 after MOG

immunization. (A-F) Phenotypic characterization of CD4+ T cell subsets distinguished by HELIOS, Foxp3, CD44 and CD62L by flow cytometry. (G-L) Phenotypic characterization of CD8+ T cell subsets distinguished by HELIOS, Foxp3, CD44 and

CD62L by flow cytometry (M-O) Multidimensional flow cytometry analysis of TCRb-immune cells in CNS on day 13 after immunization. (M) Unsupervised clustering and (N) heat map with marker expression in the individual immune cell clusters. (O) Proportion of each of the clusters in Cre- compared to Cre+ mice (N = 6 mice / group).